

In Memoriam Prof. Dr. İbrahim Mete Mısırlıođlu (1972–2021)

İbrahim Mete Mısırlıođlu was a world renowned earthworm taxonomist, and a valuable scientist both in Turkey and internationally. He passed away unexpectedly in 02. May 2021 at age of 49. He will be remembered as a leading soil zoologist in Turkey and the Middle East due to his outstanding contributions to oligochaete taxonomy, faunistics and biogeography and as a good person because of his charming personality and helpfulness.

İbrahim Mete Mısırlıođlu was born in 05. September 1972. He started his studies at the biology department of Anadolu University in 1989 and graduated from there in 1993. After graduating from the department of biology, he started his

master's degree in the biology department of the Eskişehir Osmangazi University and graduated in 1995. He earned his Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) degree at the same university in 2001 and ever since he was working there, first as a research assistant at the Department of Biology, Science and Literature Faculty of Eskişehir Osman Gazi University. In 2013 he was appointed as an Associate Professor and in 2018 received the title of Full Professor.

He was working as a farabi coordinator between 2009–2021, and between 2013–2021 as the head of the biology department. The rapid rise in his academic career shows how talented a scientist he was.

During his academic career, Prof. Mısırlıoğlu has written 10 books, 1 chapter and some 90 articles, making great contributions to the knowledge on earthworms, especially in Turkey and the East Mediterranean. Besides his scientific activity he was a prolific popular science writer as well writing some 50 popular science articles on diverse topics like the Anatolian leopard or loss of Anatolian biodiversity.

He was full of plans, especially writing a book on earthworms for children and also a review paper on the world distribution of earthworm families and genera. Unfortunately, these plans

remain to be accomplished by his students and colleagues around the world.

Certainly, Prof. Dr. İbrahim Mete Mısırlıoğlu will sadly be missed by us, his students, and also his colleagues and friends both in Turkey and abroad.

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Complete list of publications of Prof. Dr. İbrahim Mete Mısırlıoğlu

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